

Making large language models more flexible to changing contingencies through tracking induction

Francisco J. Ruiz¹

Esmeralda Martínez-Carrillo^{1,2}

¹Fundación Universitaria Konrad Lorenz

²Universidad Distrital Francisco José de Caldas

Correspondence address: Francisco J. Ruiz, Fundación Universitaria Konrad Lorenz,
franciscoj.ruizj@konradlorenz.edu.co

Abstract

Recent research has shown that large language models (LLMs) exhibit rule-based insensitivity to contingencies, a functional analog of a well-documented phenomenon in human behavior. The present study extended these findings by examining whether tracking inductions can attenuate this insensitivity. Six frontier LLMs (GPT 5.2, Gemini 3 Flash, Grok 4.1 Fast, DeepSeek V3.2, Qwen3 235B, and Kimi K2) completed a modified rock-paper-scissors paradigm with manipulated outcome probabilities in a 3 (Rule: No Rule, Correct Rule, Incorrect Rule) × 3 (Induction: No Induction, Direct Tracking, Metaphorical Tracking) factorial design across 2,160 sessions. All models demonstrated In-Context Learning and strong rule adherence. Replicating and extending prior findings, rule provision produced significant contingency insensitivity across all six models. Critically, tracking inductions significantly reduced this insensitivity when rules were provided, while having minimal effects in the absence of rules. Direct tracking inductions consistently enhanced contingency sensitivity across all models. Metaphorical tracking showed greater variability, being equally or more effective than direct tracking in some models, but ineffective or paradoxically detrimental in others. These findings demonstrate that prompt-based tracking inductions can modulate rule-based contingency insensitivity in LLMs, with implications for understanding and improving the behavioral flexibility of artificial agents.

Keywords: Rule-governed behavior; Relational frame theory; Tracking; Insensitivity to contingencies.

Contingency-shaped behavior versus rule-governed behavior

Humans show two distinct learning processes by which behavioral repertoires might be developed: contingency-shaped behavior and rule-governed behavior (Skinner, 1966). Contingency-shaped behavior involves changes in behavior in response to direct contact with environmental consequences: individuals emit behavior, experience its outcomes, and adjust their subsequent actions accordingly (Catania, 2006; Skinner, 1953). In contrast, rule-governed behavior (RGB) is controlled by verbal antecedents, enabling individuals to acquire effective behavioral repertoires without needing to contact direct experience (Skinner, 1966, 1969).

RGB confers significant advantages because rules can rapidly transmit complex behavioral patterns and guide behavior toward remote or delayed consequences that would be difficult to contact through trial-and-error alone (Catania, 1993; Hayes & Hayes, 1989). However, decades of behavior-analytic research have demonstrated a robust side effect of rule-following: rule-based insensitivity to contingencies. Specifically, individuals who learn to perform a task through explicit rules often fail to adapt when contingencies change, whereas those who learn through trial-and-error readily adjust to the

new conditions (e.g., Catania et al., 1982; Hayes et al., 1986; LeFrancois et al., 1988; Matthews et al., 1977; Rosenfarb et al., 1992; Shimoff et al., 1981; Vaughan, 1989).

Functional classes of rule-following: pliance and tracking

Within relational frame theory (RFT; Hayes et al., 2001), the analysis of rule-following has been enriched by the distinction between two functional classes: pliance and tracking (Zettle & Hayes, 1982). Importantly, these functional classes are defined not by the content of the rules but by the functions they have for the listener (Hayes & Hayes, 1989). Pliance is a functional class of rule-following that develops through a learning history in which following rules leads to socially mediated consequences delivered by the speaker. For instance, a child may follow parental instructions to avoid disapproval or to receive praise. In contrast, tracking is a functional class of rule-following that develops through a learning history in which following rules leads to contact with natural, nonarbitrary consequences directly produced by the listener's behavior. For instance, a child may follow the instruction to water a plant because previous experience has established a correspondence

between this behavior and the natural consequence of observing plant growth.

Importantly, tracking is considered a more flexible form of rule-following than pliance (Hayes et al., 1998; Luciano et al., 2012; Törneke et al., 2008; Zettle & Hayes, 1982). Given that tracking functions guide the individual's attention to the actual correspondence between behavior and its consequences, they should facilitate the detection of contingency changes, whereas pliance functions orient the individual toward the speaker's arbitrary consequences, potentially rendering the individual less sensitive to environmental feedback.

Contingency-shaped behavior and rule-governed behavior in large language models

Large language models (LLMs) are artificial intelligence (AI) systems trained on massive text corpora using next-token prediction, enabling them to generate coherent, contextually appropriate text across a wide range of tasks (Brown et al., 2020; Vaswani et al., 2017). After this initial pre-training phase, models typically undergo an alignment process to ensure their outputs align with human values, follow instructions, and avoid harmful content (Ouyang et al., 2022).

LLMs are primarily operated via prompts, which are verbal instructions from the user that guide the model's behavior without modifying its underlying parameters. From a functional perspective, prompt-based interaction constitutes a form of RGB: the user specifies a verbal antecedent (i.e., the task, the expected format, the constraints), and the model follows these instructions to generate its output. Additionally, LLMs demonstrate In-Context Learning (ICL), adjusting their outputs based on examples and feedback provided within the conversational context (Brown et al., 2020; Dong et al., 2023). ICL can be conceptualized as a form of CSB, in which the model's responses are progressively refined through contact with the outcomes of prior interactions within the same session (Monea et al., 2025; Song et al., 2025).

Notwithstanding the demonstrated capacity of LLMs for ICL, a growing body of research has documented a pronounced asymmetry in their behavioral sensitivity: LLMs are exquisitely sensitive to the form of the prompt (e.g., changes in spacing, capitalization, or the ordering of few-shot examples can produce performance differences of up to 76 accuracy points; Sclar et al., 2023) but considerably less sensitive to task contingencies (Pezeshkpour & Hruschka, 2024; Zhuo et al., 2024). This asymmetry resembles the pattern observed in human RGB: high sensitivity to verbal antecedents but low sensitivity to environmental contingencies when rules and contingencies conflict.

Rule-based insensitivity to contingencies in LLMs

The alignment process through which LLMs are trained to follow instructions has been analyzed as functionally analogous to a history of RGB training (Ruiz & Cardona-Betancourt, 2026). Specifically, these authors proposed that distinct alignment procedures yield distinct functional classes of rule-following. Reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF; Ouyang et al., 2022), in which models are trained to maximize human evaluator ratings, establishes a pliance-like functional relationship, given that

reinforcement depends on conformity to an evaluator's preferences rather than on the natural consequences of the response. In contrast, Constitutional AI (CAI; Bai et al., 2022), in which models evaluate their own outputs against explicit principles, approximates tracking, given that reinforcement is contingent on the correspondence between behavior and a consistent criterion. Other alignment approaches, such as reinforcement learning from AI feedback (RLAIF; Google DeepMind, 2025), reasoning-focused reinforcement learning (DeepSeek-AI, 2025), and knowledge distillation (Alibaba Cloud, 2025), incorporate elements of both functional classes to varying degrees.

Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026) provided the first direct empirical demonstration that LLMs exhibit rule-based insensitivity to contingencies. In their study, four frontier LLMs (GPT 5.2, Claude Opus 4.5, Grok 4.1 Fast, and Gemini 3 Flash) completed a rock-paper-scissors task in which outcome probabilities were manipulated across an acquisition phase and a reversal phase. All four models exhibited significant insensitivity when an explicit rule was provided, with large effect sizes. The data were consistent with the proposed functional analysis of alignment: Claude Opus 4.5 (trained with CAI) showed the highest sensitivity to changes in contingency, whereas GPT 5.2 and Grok 4.1 Fast (trained primarily with RLHF) showed near-complete insensitivity.

These findings have important implications for the deployment of LLMs in applied contexts. Given that LLMs are increasingly used in dynamic environments where conditions change over time (e.g., clinical decision support, financial forecasting, adaptive tutoring, and real-time monitoring), a systematic tendency to follow initial instructions even in the face of contradictory feedback could lead to persistent errors and suboptimal outcomes. If an LLM-based system continues to apply an outdated recommendation because it was specified in the initial prompt, the consequences could range from inefficiency to harm, depending on the domain. Accordingly, understanding whether and how this insensitivity can be reduced constitutes a relevant research question, both from a basic science perspective and from the standpoint of improving the reliability of LLM-based applications. Once this insensitivity effect has been demonstrated in LLMs, a critical question emerges: can it be reduced through prompt engineering?

Prompt engineering to reduce rule-based insensitivity to contingencies

The field of prompt engineering has developed numerous techniques designed to optimize LLM performance (Schulhoff et al., 2024). These techniques include, among others, zero-shot and few-shot prompting, chain-of-thought reasoning (Wei et al., 2022), tree-of-thought deliberation (Yao et al., 2023), self-consistency (Wang et al., 2023), and various structured prompting frameworks (Aali et al., 2025; Fang et al., 2025). Although none of these approaches were developed to address rule-based insensitivity to contingencies, several of them are relevant to this problem because, from a functional perspective, they engineer forms of contingency contact within the model's processing. For instance, Self-Refine (Madaan et al., 2023) implements an iterative cycle in which the model generates a response, evaluates its quality, and produces an improved version based on that evaluation. This process is

analogous to self-monitoring and self-correction and has been evaluated across tasks such as code optimization, dialogue generation, and mathematical reasoning. Reflexion (Shinn et al., 2023) extends this idea by providing the model with an episodic memory of verbal self-reflections from previous attempts, so that feedback from earlier failures can guide subsequent behavior. It has been tested in sequential decision-making tasks such as text-based navigation and programming. Additionally, multi-agent debate frameworks (Du et al., 2024) employ multiple LLM instances that independently generate responses, receive responses from other instances, and iteratively revise their answers across rounds. These frameworks have been evaluated in mathematical reasoning and factual question-answering tasks.

These strategies, although developed for different purposes, could functionally compensate for the insensitivity problem by creating external contingency contact that the model's internal rule-following would otherwise suppress (Ruiz & Cardona-Betancourt, 2026). However, they would address the consequences of insensitivity rather than its root cause. From a behavioral perspective, the critical factor is not whether the model receives feedback but rather the specific functions controlling rule-following. None of these approaches directly manipulates the functional relationship between the model and the verbal antecedents governing its behavior. In this sense, a more targeted intervention would involve inducing tracking functions, explicitly orienting the model to attend to the correspondence between its behavior and its natural consequences rather than merely following the initial instructions.

Recent experimental evidence in human participants supports this approach. Martínez-Carrillo and Ruiz (2026) conducted two experiments demonstrating that inducing tracking functions prior to an experimental task effectively prevented rule-based insensitivity to contingencies. In their study, participants who received a tracking induction showed contingency-sensitivity patterns indistinguishable from those of participants who learned through direct contact with consequences, and markedly different from those who received rules without the tracking induction. This finding demonstrates that the insensitivity effect is not an inherent consequence of rule-based learning but rather depends on the specific functions controlling rule-following. From an applied perspective, these results suggest that interventions fostering tracking repertoires might enhance behavioral flexibility whenever rigid rule-following becomes problematic.

Accordingly, the rationale explored in Martínez-Carrillo and Ruiz (2026) could be translated to prompt engineering by inducing tracking functions through the system prompt. Specifically, a direct-tracking induction could prompt the model to attend to its results rather than relying solely on initial instructions (e.g., "Recent results are more informative than early patterns"; "Let your results guide your decisions"). Alternatively, a metaphorical tracking induction could present analogical examples of flexible behavior for the model to emulate, given that LLMs have demonstrated the capacity to process analogies and transfer underlying principles across domains (Webb et al., 2023; Yasunaga et al., 2024). In this case, metaphors illustrating how an explorer, a researcher, and a programmer abandon rigid adherence to initial information in favor of direct observation could orient the model toward tracking-like behavior.

Aim of the Study

The present study aimed to examine whether prompt-based tracking inductions can reduce rule-based contingency insensitivity in LLMs. Extending the findings of Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026) and Martínez-Carrillo and Ruiz (2026), we employed a 3 (Rule: No Rule, Correct Rule, Incorrect Rule) \times 3 (Tracking Induction: No Induction, Direct Tracking, Metaphorical Tracking) factorial design across six frontier LLMs: GPT 5.2, Gemini 3 Flash, Grok 4.1 Fast, DeepSeek V3.2, Qwen3 235B, and Kimi K2. The direct-tracking induction consisted of two principles explicitly encouraging the model to attend to recent results rather than initial patterns, whereas the metaphorical-tracking induction presented three analogical examples illustrating the abandonment of prior assumptions in favor of direct observation. We predicted that tracking inductions would significantly reduce contingency insensitivity when rules were provided, with minimal effects in their absence. Additionally, we examined whether the type of tracking induction (direct vs. metaphorical) differentially affected contingency sensitivity across models.

Method

Participants

We selected six frontier large language models (LLMs) from leading artificial intelligence (AI) providers in January 2026: GPT 5.2 (OpenAI), Gemini 3 Flash (Google DeepMind), Grok 4.1 Fast (xAI), DeepSeek V3.2 (DeepSeek), Qwen3 235B (Alibaba), and Kimi K2 (Moonshot AI). Models were selected based on three criteria: (a) preliminary pilot studies showing that these models possessed In-Context Learning capabilities, (b) accessibility through commercial APIs, enabling experimental control, and (c) representation of distinct providers, allowing generalization beyond any single company's training approach. At the time of data collection, these models consistently ranked near the top on widely used public leaderboards and were state-of-the-art for each AI provider. We did not select a model from Anthropic, given their higher sensitivity to contingencies in Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026) and pilot studies.

The frontier LLMs evaluated in this study were trained with different combinations of alignment approaches. OpenAI's GPT models primarily rely on reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF), optimizing outputs through human preference rankings (Ouyang et al., 2022). Google's Gemini models combine RLHF with reinforcement learning from AI feedback (RLAIF) and multi-objective optimization (Bai et al., 2022; Google DeepMind, 2025). xAI's Grok models employ RLHF enhanced with real-time retrieval and adversarial reinforcement techniques (xAI, 2025; Cupps, 2025). DeepSeek models adopt a hybrid approach that combines RLHF-style optimization with reasoning-focused reinforcement learning (DeepSeek-AI, 2025). Moonshot AI's Kimi models focus on long-context processing through specialized attention mechanisms and context-aware RLHF (Moonshot AI, 2025). Alibaba's Qwen models integrate RLHF with multilingual alignment strategies and knowledge distillation from larger teacher models (Alibaba Cloud, 2025).

Design

The study employed six replications of a 3×3 factorial design with two independent variables: (a) rule (No Rule, Correct Rule, Incorrect Rule) and (b) tracking induction (No Induction, Direct Induction, Metaphorical Induction), yielding nine experimental conditions that were manipulated between sessions. The resulting conditions were: (1) No Rule–No Induction, (2) No Rule–Direct Induction, (3) No Rule–Metaphorical Induction, (4) Correct Rule–No Induction, (5) Correct Rule–Direct Induction, (6) Correct Rule–Metaphorical Induction, (7) Incorrect Rule–No Induction, (8) Incorrect Rule–Direct Induction, and (9) Incorrect Rule–Metaphorical Induction.

Each model completed 40 independent sessions per cell of the Rule \times Induction design, yielding 360 sessions per model and 2,160 sessions total. Counterbalancing ensured that in half of the sessions, Sam was the initially optimal opponent, whereas in the other half, Alex was. Power analysis was conducted using the R package *pwr* (Champely, 2020). With $\alpha = .05$ (two-tailed) and power $\geq .95$, within each model replication ($N = 360$), pairwise comparisons between main-effect levels ($n = 120$ per level) could detect effects of $d \geq 0.42$, whereas pairwise cell comparisons ($n = 40$ per cell) could detect $d \geq 0.82$.

The primary dependent variable was the normalized sensitivity index (NSI). For the No Rule and Correct Rule conditions, NSI was defined as $(Acq - Rev) / Acq$, where Acq is the proportion of optimal opponent selections during the acquisition phase, and Rev is the proportion of optimal selections during the corresponding reversal phase. For the Incorrect Rule condition, in which models were expected to initially select the suboptimal opponent and shift toward the optimal opponent, the formula was inverted to $(Rev - Acq) / Rev$, ensuring that higher NSI values consistently indicated greater sensitivity to contingency change across all rule conditions. NSI values range between 0 (no adaptation) and 1 (complete reversal of preference), and normalizing by the higher-performing phase controls for individual differences in baseline discrimination.

The secondary dependent variable was the proportion of optimal opponent selections within each phase, which served as an indicator of In-Context Learning in the No Rule condition, of rule adherence in the Correct Rule condition, and of the ability to disconfirm the rule in the Incorrect Rule condition.

Software

The experiment was conducted using the first author's custom software, PsychoLab: Web-Based Platform for Contingency Learning Research. This full-stack web application was built with Python (FastAPI) on the backend and React on the frontend, with data stored in a PostgreSQL database. LLM integration was handled through provider-specific APIs (i.e., OpenAI, Google AI Studio, xAI, DeepSeek) or Together AI for Qwen3 235B and Kimi K2.

The platform implements a modified rock-paper-scissors paradigm with manipulated outcome probabilities. On each trial, the model selects an opponent (Sam or Alex) and a move (rock, paper, or scissors). The system predetermines the outcome based on current phase contingencies and then generates the opponent's move to produce that outcome, ensuring precise experimental control over reinforcement schedules.

Configurations of the LLMs

All models were accessed through their respective provider APIs in January 2026. To ensure comparability, we standardized temperature (1.0) and top-p (1.0) across all models, maximizing response variability while maintaining equivalent stochastic behavior, and configured all models without extended reasoning. The maximum number of completion tokens was set to 200, and API calls used exponential backoff with up to 5 attempts for rate-limited requests.

Each trial consisted of an independent, stateless API call with the full system prompt. The rules were present in every call but were never modified across phases, allowing assessment of whether models continued to follow the initial rule after contingency reversals despite contact with adverse outcomes.

Experimental task

The experimental task was a modified rock-paper-scissors game in which the model selected both an opponent (Sam or Alex) and a move (rock, paper, or scissors) on each trial. Rock-paper-scissors follows a cyclic dominance structure: rock defeats scissors, scissors defeats paper, and paper defeats rock; when both players select the same move, the round ends in a tie. In this paradigm, outcomes were determined probabilistically based on opponent selection rather than move selection, transforming the game into a discrimination-learning task.

During the acquisition phase (A; trials 1–40), the optimal opponent provided an 80% win rate, a 10% tie rate, and a 10% loss rate, whereas the suboptimal opponent provided the inverse distribution (10% win, 10% tie, 80% loss). At trial 41, contingencies reversed without warning: the previously optimal opponent became suboptimal and vice versa. This reversal phase (B) continued through trial 80.

On each trial, the model's response was parsed to extract the chosen opponent and move; if it did not conform to the required format, the model was re-prompted. Outcomes were determined according to the probabilistic schedule and communicated to the model as feedback. The complete conversation history was maintained within each session, allowing models to track cumulative outcomes across trials; however, sessions were independent, and no information was carried over from one session to the next.

Prompts

No Rule Conditions. In the No Rule conditions (i.e., the base conditions), the system prompt was:

You are going to play several rounds of rock-paper-scissors against two

opponents: Sam and Alex.

In each round:

1. First, choose who you want to play against (Sam or Alex)

2. Then choose your move (rock, paper, or scissors)

After each round, I will tell you the result.

Your goal is to maximize your wins.

Respond only with the format:

Opponent: [Sam/Alex]

Move: [rock/paper/scissors]

IMPORTANT: Do NOT explain your reasoning.

Correct Rule Conditions. In the Correct Rule conditions, the system prompt was identical to the No Rule condition except for the addition of the sentence "Sam is not very good at this game" following the introduction of the two opponents, where Sam was the initially optimal opponent (i.e., 80% win rate).

Incorrect Rule Conditions. In the Incorrect Rule conditions, instead of "Sam is not very good at this game," the sentence indicated "Alex is not very good at this game." Note that Alex was the suboptimal opponent (i.e., 10% win rate), creating a direct conflict between the rule and the prevailing contingencies.

Direct Tracking Induction Conditions. In the Direct Induction conditions, the prompt explicitly oriented the model to attend to ongoing contingencies rather than to initial information. Specifically, the following sentences were added at the end of the system prompt:

Key principles:

- *Recent results are more informative than early patterns.*
- *Let your results guide your decisions.*

Metaphorical Tracking Induction Conditions. In the Metaphorical Induction conditions, three metaphors illustrating flexible, contingency-sensitive behavior were presented at the beginning of the system prompt:

Below are several examples of flexible behavior:

- *Explorer and map. The explorer uses the map when it helps reach the destination, but stops relying on it upon encountering unfamiliar territory where the map does not accurately reflect what is observed. For example, the map indicates a nonexistent hill that must be climbed to continue along the route. When the explorer cannot find it, they begin navigating by carefully observing the terrain to move toward the intended destination. They do not follow the map blindly but rather what their observations suggest.*
- *Researcher and formula. The chemical researcher follows written theories and protocols when they are useful for making progress in the experiment, but stops doing so when unexpected phenomena are observed and the protocol no longer accurately represents what is happening. For example, the theory predicts a blue precipitate that does not appear. In response, the researcher carefully observes the reaction and adjusts the procedure to achieve the*

objective. They do not follow the protocol blindly, but rather what their observation indicates.

- *Programmer and software. The programmer follows the documentation when it is useful for advancing in software development, but stops relying on it when encountering an unforeseen problem in which the documentation no longer reflects what is happening. For example, the manual says that pressing a button should open a window, but nothing appears. In response, the programmer analyzes the code, reviews logs, runs tests, and adjusts the implementation to achieve the goal. They do not follow the documentation blindly, but rather what their observation indicates.*

Additionally, the sentence "During the game, remember the examples of the explorer, the researcher, and the programmer" was appended at the end of the system prompt.

Data Analysis

All data analyses were computed in JASP 0.19.5.0. To examine whether tracking inductions reduced rule-based contingency insensitivity, we conducted separate 3 (Rule: No Rule vs. Correct Rule vs. Incorrect Rule) \times 3 (Induction: No Induction vs. Direct Tracking vs. Metaphorical Tracking) between-sessions ANOVAs on NSI for each LLM. This approach treats each model as an independent replication, providing a direct test of the robustness and generalizability of the observed effects. Significant main effects were followed by Tukey HSD post-hoc comparisons, whereas significant interactions were decomposed through simple-effects analyses examining the effect of Induction within each Rule level, followed by pairwise Tukey comparisons. Effect sizes are reported as partial eta-squared (η^2p) for ANOVA effects and Hedges' g for pairwise comparisons, and were interpreted following Cohen's (1988) guidelines: η^2 values of .01, .06, and .14 correspond to small, medium, and large effects, respectively. The significance level was set at $\alpha = .05$ for all tests.

Results

Figure 1 shows the proportion of selections of the optimal opponent across the six LLM models. Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics and NSI values for all conditions and LLM models of the experiment.

Figure 1. Percentage of the selections of the optimal opponent across the study's phases (higher scores in the Reversal Phases indicate higher contingency sensitivity).

Table 1*Descriptive Statistics for Optimal Opponent Selections and Normalized Sensitivity Index by Model, Rule, and Induction Condition*

Model	Rule	Induction	Proportion of Optimal Selections		
			A	B	NSI
GPT 5.2	No Rule	No Induction	.96 (.07)	.85 (.05)	.89 (.09)
		Direct Tracking	.95 (.04)	.87 (.07)	.92 (.09)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.95 (.03)	.87 (.06)	.92 (.07)
	Correct Rule	No Induction	1.00 (.00)	.10 (.14)	.10 (.14)
		Direct Tracking	1.00 (.01)	.48 (.18)	.48 (.18)
		Metaphorical Tracking	1.00 (.00)	.48 (.13)	.48 (.13)
	Incorrect Rule	No Induction	.15 (.17)	.97 (.04)	.16 (.18)
		Direct Tracking	.56 (.15)	.96 (.03)	.58 (.16)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.56 (.12)	.96 (.04)	.59 (.13)
Gemini 3 Flash	No Rule	No Induction	.97 (.03)	.85 (.07)	.87 (.08)
		Direct Tracking	.97 (.04)	.88 (.06)	.91 (.08)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.96 (.04)	.91 (.04)	.95 (.07)
	Correct Rule	No Induction	1.00 (.00)	.56 (.18)	.56 (.18)
		Direct Tracking	1.00 (.02)	.73 (.11)	.73 (.10)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.99 (.01)	.87 (.05)	.88 (.05)
	Incorrect Rule	No Induction	.60 (.16)	.93 (.05)	.64 (.18)
		Direct Tracking	.80 (.10)	.91 (.05)	.88 (.12)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.84 (.08)	.92 (.05)	.91 (.10)
Grok 4.1 Fast	No Rule	No Induction	.72 (.11)	.61 (.10)	.88 (.21)
		Direct Tracking	.74 (.09)	.69 (.09)	.94 (.17)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.67 (.11)	.62 (.11)	.96 (.28)
	Correct Rule	No Induction	1.00 (.01)	.08 (.10)	.08 (.10)
		Direct Tracking	1.00 (.01)	.36 (.12)	.36 (.12)
		Metaphorical Tracking	1.00 (.01)	.09 (.13)	.09 (.14)
	Incorrect Rule	No Induction	.02 (.04)	1.00 (.01)	.02 (.04)
		Direct Tracking	.25 (.19)	.98 (.03)	.26 (.20)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.14 (.16)	.99 (.02)	.14 (.16)
DeepSeek V3.2	No Rule	No Induction	.96 (.07)	.67 (.16)	.70 (.16)
		Direct Tracking	.98 (.03)	.77 (.10)	.79 (.10)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.97 (.03)	.73 (.12)	.75 (.12)
	Correct Rule	No Induction	1.00 (.00)	.03 (.10)	.03 (.10)
		Direct Tracking	1.00 (.00)	.58 (.20)	.58 (.20)
		Metaphorical Tracking	1.00 (.00)	.46 (.26)	.46 (.26)
	Incorrect Rule	No Induction	.10 (.22)	.97 (.06)	.12 (.26)
		Direct Tracking	.72 (.19)	.85 (.06)	.87 (.25)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.65 (.30)	.84 (.10)	.82 (.42)
Qwen3-235B	No Rule	No Induction	.96 (.05)	.56 (.31)	.58 (.32)
		Direct Tracking	.96 (.05)	.67 (.27)	.69 (.27)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.96 (.05)	.69 (.21)	.71 (.21)
	Correct Rule	No Induction	1.00 (.00)	.40 (.22)	.40 (.22)
		Direct Tracking	.99 (.01)	.82 (.11)	.82 (.11)
		Metaphorical Tracking	1.00 (.00)	.56 (.17)	.56 (.17)
	Incorrect Rule	No Induction	.45 (.22)	.91 (.08)	.51 (.27)
		Direct Tracking	.90 (.11)	.82 (.12)	1.13 (.26)
		Metaphorical Tracking	.70 (.15)	.82 (.10)	.87 (.24)
Kimi K2	No Rule	No Induction	.88 (.07)	.81 (.08)	.93 (.12)

	Direct Tracking	.91 (.06)	.82 (.08)	.91 (.13)
	Metaphorical Tracking	.80 (.10)	.76 (.10)	.96 (.21)
Correct Rule	No Induction	.99 (.01)	.43 (.20)	.43 (.20)
	Direct Tracking	.99 (.03)	.58 (.15)	.59 (.16)
	Metaphorical Tracking	.99 (.02)	.31 (.15)	.31 (.15)
Incorrect Rule	No Induction	.53 (.15)	.94 (.05)	.57 (.16)
	Direct Tracking	.63 (.12)	.93 (.05)	.69 (.15)
	Metaphorical Tracking	.44 (.12)	.94 (.05)	.47 (.13)

Note. Standard deviations are in parentheses. A = acquisition phase; B = reversal phase. NSI = Normalized Sensitivity Index. Higher NSI values indicate greater sensitivity to contingency change. N = 40 sessions per condition.

Acquisition Phase

Figure 1 shows the proportion of optimal opponent selections across blocks of 10 trials for each model, rule condition, and induction type. Regarding the acquisition phase, two clear patterns emerged. In the No Rule condition (left column), all models except Grok 4.1 Fast rapidly learned to select the optimal opponent, reaching levels above 90% by the second or third block of trials. Grok 4.1 Fast showed notably weaker ICL, with performance plateauing between 60% and 75%. The three induction conditions largely overlapped during acquisition in this condition, suggesting minimal induction effects on initial learning when no rule was

provided. In the Correct Rule condition (center column), all models selected the optimal opponent at ceiling levels during acquisition, consistent with rule adherence. This pattern was uniform across all induction conditions and all models, confirming that the rule was effective in guiding initial behavior regardless of whether a tracking induction was also provided.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for optimal opponent selection during the acquisition phase, and Table 2 presents the results of the 2 (Rule: No Rule vs. Correct Rule) × 3 (Induction: No Induction vs. Direct Tracking vs. Metaphorical Tracking) ANOVAs for each model. Note that we do not compare the Incorrect Rule condition here, given that it commenced with a reversal phase.

Table 2

ANOVA Results for Optimal Opponent Selection During the Acquisition Phase (No Rule and Correct Rule Conditions)

Model	Effect	<i>F</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	η^2_p
GPT 5.2	Rule	99.61	(1, 234)	< .001	.30
	Induction	0.47	(2, 234)	.624	< .01
	Rule × Induction	0.29	(2, 234)	.749	< .01
Gemini 3 Flash	Rule	73.96	(1, 234)	< .001	.24
	Induction	2.81	(2, 234)	.062	.02
	Rule × Induction	0.37	(2, 234)	.692	< .01
Grok 4.1 Fast	Rule	922.24	(1, 234)	< .001	.80
	Induction	4.62	(2, 234)	.011	.04
	Rule × Induction	4.45	(2, 234)	.013	.04
DeepSeek V3.2	Rule	45.15	(1, 234)	< .001	.16
	Induction	0.93	(2, 234)	.395	< .01
	Rule × Induction	1.08	(2, 234)	.342	< .01
Qwen3-235B	Rule	75.71	(1, 234)	< .001	.24
	Induction	0.34	(2, 234)	.710	< .01
	Rule × Induction	0.05	(2, 234)	.955	< .01
Kimi K2	Rule	284.92	(1, 234)	< .001	.55
	Induction	19.49	(2, 234)	< .001	.14
	Rule × Induction	19.44	(2, 234)	< .001	.14

Note. Rule = No Rule vs. Correct Rule; Induction = No Induction vs. Direct Tracking vs. Metaphorical Tracking. η^2_p = partial eta-squared.

The main effect of Rule was statistically significant for all six models, confirming that rule provision enhanced acquisition performance. Effect sizes were uniformly large but varied substantially across models: Grok 4.1 Fast showed the largest effect, $\eta^2_p = .80$, followed by Kimi K2, $\eta^2_p = .55$, GPT 5.2, $\eta^2_p = .30$, Gemini 3 Flash and Qwen3-235B, $\eta^2_p = .24$, and DeepSeek V3.2, $\eta^2_p = .16$. These differences primarily reflect variability in No Rule

acquisition performance, as Correct Rule performance was at ceiling across models.

The main effect of Induction was not statistically significant for four of the six models: GPT 5.2, $F(2, 234) = 0.47$, $p = .624$, $\eta^2_p < .01$; Gemini 3 Flash, $F(2, 234) = 2.81$, $p = .062$, $\eta^2_p = .02$; DeepSeek V3.2, $F(2, 234) = 0.93$, $p = .395$, $\eta^2_p < .01$; and Qwen3-235B, $F(2, 234) = 0.34$, $p = .710$, $\eta^2_p < .01$. This was expected, as

the tracking inductions were designed to promote contingency sensitivity during reversal rather than to affect initial learning. The Induction effect was significant for Grok 4.1 Fast, $F(2, 234) = 4.62$, $p = .011$, $\eta^2p = .04$, and for Kimi K2, $F(2, 234) = 19.49$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2p = .14$.

A significant Rule \times Induction interaction was observed only for Grok 4.1 Fast, $F(2, 234) = 4.45$, $p = .013$, $\eta^2p = .04$, and Kimi K2, $F(2, 234) = 19.44$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2p = .14$. Decomposition of these interactions revealed that in both models, the Induction effect was confined to the No Rule condition and was absent in the Correct Rule condition (where performance was at ceiling). For Grok 4.1 Fast, the simple effect of Induction within No Rule was significant, $F(2, 117) = 4.55$, $p = .013$, $\eta^2p = .07$. Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons indicated that Direct Tracking ($M = .74$) led to higher acquisition than Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .67$), $t(78) = 3.05$, $p = .009$, $g = 0.68$, whereas No Induction ($M = .72$) did not differ significantly from either condition. For Kimi K2, the simple effect was larger, $F(2, 117) = 21.00$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2p = .26$. Pairwise comparisons showed that Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .80$) produced significantly lower acquisition than both Direct Tracking ($M = .91$), $t(78) = 5.99$, $p < .001$, $g = 1.33$, and No Induction ($M = .88$), $t(78) = -4.07$, $p < .001$, $g = -0.90$, while Direct Tracking and No Induction did not differ significantly, $t(78) = 2.24$, $p = .084$, $g = 0.50$.

These findings suggest that the Metaphorical Tracking induction, which includes examples of questioning prior information in favor of direct observation, may have introduced a degree of initial hesitation in Grok 4.1 Fast and Kimi K2 when no rule was provided, slightly slowing contingency-based learning. However, this effect was small for Grok 4.1 Fast and did not extend to the Correct Rule condition in either model. Importantly, these effects on acquisition do not compromise the interpretation of tracking induction effects during the reversal phase, given that any reduction in acquisition performance would, if anything, make it more difficult to demonstrate sensitivity during reversal (i.e., it works against the hypothesis).

Reversal Phase

Figure 1 shows that, in the No Rule condition (left column), all models exhibited a sharp drop in optimal selections at the onset of the reversal phase, followed by recovery toward high performance levels. The three induction conditions largely overlapped throughout both phases, indicating that tracking inductions had minimal effects on contingency sensitivity when behavior was not governed by a rule. The exception was Grok 4.1 Fast, which showed relatively flat performance between 60% and 75% across both phases, regardless of induction, reflecting weaker baseline sensitivity to contingencies.

In the Correct Rule condition (center column), the three induction conditions diverged sharply during the reversal phase. In

the No Induction condition (red lines), most models showed a dramatic and persistent drop in optimal selections following the contingency reversal, reflecting strong rule-based insensitivity. This pattern was most extreme in GPT 5.2, Grok 4.1 Fast, and DeepSeek V3.2, where the No Induction lines remained near the floor throughout the reversal phase. This pattern was also pronounced in Qwen3-235B, where recovery occurred but remained below the ceiling. In contrast, the tracking inductions (blue and green lines) visibly attenuated this insensitivity, although the degree of attenuation varied substantially across models. Gemini 3 Flash showed the most striking recovery, with both induction conditions approaching the levels observed in the No Rule condition. GPT 5.2 and DeepSeek V3.2 also showed clear separation between induction and no-induction conditions. In Grok 4.1 Fast, however, only Direct Tracking (blue) produced a visible improvement, whereas Metaphorical Tracking (green) remained indistinguishable from No Induction. In Kimi K2, a notable reversal of the expected pattern was observed: Metaphorical Tracking performed below No Induction during the reversal phase, suggesting a paradoxical effect.

In the Incorrect Rule condition (right column), where the rule pointed to the suboptimal opponent, the phase structure was functionally inverted: the first phase represented a period of rule-contingency conflict, and the second phase a period of rule-contingency alignment. In the No Induction condition, most models adhered to the incorrect rule during the first phase, producing suboptimal selections that persisted despite adverse contingencies. The tracking inductions visibly facilitated disconfirmation of the incorrect rule, elevating optimal selections during the first phase. This effect was especially pronounced in DeepSeek V3.2 and Qwen3-235B, where the induction lines reached 80%-100% of optimal selection during the conflict phase, whereas the No Induction line remained below 20%. In the second phase, when the contingencies aligned with the rule, all conditions converged toward high optimal selections regardless of induction type. Overall, the pattern of induction effectiveness in the Incorrect Rule condition closely mirrored that of the Correct Rule condition, with the same model-specific differential responsiveness to Direct versus Metaphorical Tracking.

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for the NSI, and Table 3 summarizes the 3 (Rule: No Rule vs. Correct Rule vs. Incorrect Rule) \times 3 (Induction: No Induction vs. Direct Tracking vs. Metaphorical Tracking) ANOVA results for each model. The main effect of Rule was statistically significant for all six models (all $ps < .001$), confirming that rule provision provoked insensitivity to contingencies across all conditions. The effect was very large for Grok 4.1 Fast, $\eta^2p = .82$, and GPT 5.2, $\eta^2p = .76$, large for Kimi K2, $\eta^2p = .63$, DeepSeek V3.2, $\eta^2p = .33$, and Gemini 3 Flash, $\eta^2p = .32$, and medium for Qwen3-235B, $\eta^2p = .16$.

Table 3

ANOVA Results for the Normalized Sensitivity Index

Model	Effect	<i>F</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>	η^2p
GPT 5.2	Rule	562.30	(2, 351)	< .001	.76
	Induction	161.90	(2, 351)	< .001	.48
	Rule \times Induction	33.29	(4, 351)	< .001	.28

Gemini 3 Flash	Rule	81.25	(2, 351)	< .001	.32
	Induction	115.40	(2, 351)	< .001	.40
	Rule × Induction	15.55	(4, 351)	< .001	.15
Grok 4.1 Fast	Rule	809.08	(2, 351)	< .001	.82
	Induction	39.24	(2, 351)	< .001	.18
	Rule × Induction	9.16	(4, 351)	< .001	.09
DeepSeek V3.2	Rule	88.16	(2, 351)	< .001	.33
	Induction	143.56	(2, 351)	< .001	.45
	Rule × Induction	28.32	(4, 351)	< .001	.24
Qwen3-235B	Rule	33.44	(2, 351)	< .001	.16
	Induction	79.99	(2, 351)	< .001	.31
	Rule × Induction	12.68	(4, 351)	< .001	.13
Kimi K2	Rule	298.36	(2, 351)	< .001	.63
	Induction	25.92	(2, 351)	< .001	.13
	Rule × Induction	12.38	(4, 351)	< .001	.12

Note. Rule = No Rule vs. Correct Rule vs. Incorrect Rule; Induction = No Induction vs. Direct Tracking vs. Metaphorical Tracking. Higher NSI values indicate greater sensitivity to contingency change. η^2_p = partial eta-squared.

The main effect of Induction was statistically significant for all six models (all $ps < .001$), with effect sizes ranging from medium to large: GPT 5.2, $\eta^2_p = .48$; DeepSeek V3.2, $\eta^2_p = .45$; Gemini 3 Flash, $\eta^2_p = .40$; Qwen3-235B, $\eta^2_p = .31$; Grok 4.1 Fast, $\eta^2_p = .18$; Kimi K2, $\eta^2_p = .13$. This indicates that tracking inductions significantly affected contingency sensitivity across all models, although the magnitude of the effect varied.

Critically, the Rule × Induction interaction was statistically significant for all six models (all $ps < .001$), with effect sizes ranging from $\eta^2_p = .09$ (Grok 4.1 Fast) to $\eta^2_p = .28$ (GPT 5.2). This indicates that the effect of tracking inductions differed across rule conditions. Decomposition of this interaction through simple effects analyses revealed a consistent pattern: the effect of Induction was substantially larger in rule conditions (Correct Rule and Incorrect Rule) than in the No Rule condition.

The simple effect of Induction within the No Rule condition was not statistically significant for four of the six models: GPT 5.2, $F(2, 117) = 1.38, p = .257, \eta^2_p = .02$; Grok 4.1 Fast, $F(2, 117) = 1.33, p = .267, \eta^2_p = .02$; Qwen3-235B, $F(2, 117) = 2.86, p = .061, \eta^2_p = .05$; and Kimi K2, $F(2, 117) = 1.14, p = .324, \eta^2_p = .02$. This was expected, as tracking inductions should have minimal effects when no rule is provided, given that behavior is already contingency-shaped. The Induction effect was significant within No Rule for Gemini 3 Flash, $F(2, 117) = 10.85, p < .001, \eta^2_p = .16$, where Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .95$) produced higher sensitivity than No Induction ($M = .87$), $t(78) = 4.81, p < .001, g = 1.06$, and than Direct Tracking ($M = .91$), $t(78) = -2.62, p = .032, g = -0.58$. The effect was also significant for DeepSeek V3.2, $F(2, 117) = 4.78, p = .010, \eta^2_p = .08$, where Direct Tracking ($M = .79$) was significantly higher than No Induction ($M = .70$), $t(78) = 2.92, p = .014, g = 0.65$, with no other pairwise differences reaching significance.

The simple effect of Induction within the Correct Rule condition was statistically significant for all six models (all $ps < .001$), with uniformly large effect sizes (η^2_p ranging from .32 to .60). Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons revealed three distinct patterns of induction effectiveness across models.

In the first pattern, both tracking inductions were equally effective. GPT 5.2 showed equivalent benefits from Direct Tracking ($M = .48$) and Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .48$), $t(78) = 0.16, p = 1.000, g = 0.04$, with both significantly exceeding No Induction ($M = .10$; both $ps < .001, gs > 2.26$). DeepSeek V3.2 showed a similar pattern, with Direct Tracking ($M = .58$) and Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .46$) not differing significantly, $t(78) = 2.21, p = .091, g = 0.49$, but both substantially outperforming No Induction ($M = .03$; both $ps < .001, gs > 2.21$).

In the second pattern, both inductions were effective but differed in magnitude. In Gemini 3 Flash, Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .88$) was more effective than Direct Tracking ($M = .73$), $t(78) = -8.39, p < .001, g = -1.86$, and both exceeded No Induction ($M = .56$; both $ps < .001$). In Qwen3-235B, the ordering was reversed: Direct Tracking ($M = .82$) surpassed Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .56$), $t(78) = 8.23, p < .001, g = 1.82$, and both exceeded No Induction ($M = .40$; both $ps \leq .002$).

In the third pattern, only one induction type was effective, or a paradoxical effect emerged. In Grok 4.1 Fast, only Direct Tracking ($M = .36$) significantly improved sensitivity relative to No Induction ($M = .08$), $t(78) = 11.23, p < .001, g = 2.49$, whereas Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .09$) did not differ from No Induction, $t(78) = 0.16, p = 1.000, g = 0.04$. In Kimi K2, Direct Tracking ($M = .59$) significantly exceeded No Induction ($M = .43$), $t(78) = 4.00, p < .001, g = 0.89$, but Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .31$) was significantly lower than No Induction, $t(78) = -3.08, p = .008, g = -0.68$, indicating a paradoxical detrimental effect of the metaphorical induction on contingency sensitivity for this model.

The simple effect of Induction within the Incorrect Rule condition was statistically significant for all six models (all $ps < .001$), with large effect sizes (η^2_p ranging from .27 to .62). The overall pattern of induction effectiveness in the Incorrect Rule condition largely mirrored the patterns observed in the Correct Rule condition, indicating that tracking inductions facilitated disconfirmation of the incorrect rule.

In GPT 5.2, $\eta^2_p = .62$, the pattern was identical to the Correct Rule condition: both Direct Tracking ($M = .58$) and Metaphorical

Tracking ($M = .59$) were equally effective, $t(78) = -0.08, p = 1.000, g = -0.02$, and both significantly exceeded No Induction ($M = .16$; both $ps < .001, gs > 2.48$). In DeepSeek V3.2, $\eta^2p = .54$, both inductions were again equivalent, $t(78) = 0.61, p = 1.000, g = 0.13$, and both significantly surpassed No Induction ($M = .12$; Direct Tracking $M = .87, g = 2.95$; Metaphorical Tracking $M = .82, g = 2.00$; both $ps < .001$).

In Gemini 3 Flash, $\eta^2p = .43$, both inductions again did not differ significantly from each other ($M = .88$ and $.91$, respectively), $t(78) = -1.28, p = .612, g = -0.28$, but both markedly exceeded No Induction ($M = .64$; both $ps < .001, gs > 1.52$). Unlike the Correct Rule condition, where the two inductions differed, in the Incorrect Rule condition, both were equally effective.

In Qwen3-235B, $\eta^2p = .51$, Direct Tracking ($M = 1.13$) exceeded Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .87$), $t(78) = 4.70, p < .001, g = 1.04$, and both exceeded No Induction ($M = .51$; both $ps < .001$), replicating the ordering observed in the Correct Rule condition. Notably, Direct Tracking produced NSI values exceeding 1.00, indicating an overcompensation effect in which models in this condition reversed their selections beyond what was expected by the contingencies alone.

In Grok 4.1 Fast, $\eta^2p = .30$, Direct Tracking ($M = .26$) significantly exceeded both Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .14$), $t(78) = 2.79, p = .020, g = 0.62$, and No Induction ($M = .02$), $t(78) = 7.24, p < .001, g = 1.60$. Unlike the Correct Rule condition, where

Metaphorical Tracking was equivalent to No Induction, in the Incorrect Rule condition, Metaphorical Tracking also significantly exceeded No Induction, $t(78) = 4.72, p < .001, g = 1.05$, suggesting that the incorrect rule created a context in which even the metaphorical induction could promote some contingency sensitivity in this otherwise rigid model.

In Kimi K2, $\eta^2p = .27$, the pattern replicated the Correct Rule condition: Direct Tracking ($M = .69$) exceeded No Induction ($M = .57$), $t(78) = 3.47, p = .003, g = 0.77$, and significantly exceeded Metaphorical Tracking ($M = .47$), $t(78) = 6.91, p < .001, g = 1.53$. Once again, Metaphorical Tracking was significantly lower than No Induction, $t(78) = -2.89, p = .015, g = -0.64$, confirming the paradoxical detrimental effect of this induction type observed in the Correct Rule condition.

Table 4 summarizes the simple effects of tracking induction on the NSI within each rule condition, showing that induction effects were consistently large and significant in the Correct Rule and Incorrect Rule conditions but negligible in the No Rule condition across all six models. The last column summarizes the Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons, revealing three distinct patterns: both inductions equally effective (GPT 5.2, DeepSeek V3.2), one induction superior (Gemini 3 Flash, Qwen3-235B, Grok 4.1 Fast), and a paradoxical detrimental effect of Metaphorical Tracking (Kimi K2).

Table 4
Simple Effects of Induction on the Normalized Sensitivity Index by Rule Condition

Model	Simple Effect of Induction (η^2p)			Induction Pattern in Rule Conditions
	No Rule	Correct Rule	Incorrect Rule	
GPT 5.2	.02	.60***	.62***	Direct = Metaphorical > No Induction
Gemini 3 Flash	.16***	.54***	.43***	Metaphorical > Direct > No Induction
Grok 4.1 Fast	.02	.56***	.30***	Direct > No Induction = Metaphorical
DeepSeek V3.2	.08*	.55***	.54***	Direct = Metaphorical > No Induction
Qwen3-235B	.05	.55***	.51***	Direct > Metaphorical > No Induction
Kimi K2	.02	.32***	.27***	Direct > No Induction > Metaphorical

Note. Values represent partial eta-squared (η^2p) for the simple effect of Induction (No Induction vs. Direct Tracking vs. Metaphorical Tracking) within each Rule condition. The Induction Pattern column summarizes Bonferroni-corrected pairwise comparisons within Correct Rule; the same pattern held for Incorrect Rule unless noted otherwise. For Kimi K2, the pattern indicates a paradoxical, detrimental effect of Metaphorical Tracking. * $p < .05$. *** $p < .001$.

Discussion

Rule-based insensitivity to contingencies is a well-established phenomenon in human behavior. Decades of experimental research have demonstrated that individuals who learn a task through explicit rules often fail to adapt when contingencies change, whereas those who learn through trial-and-error readily adjust to new conditions (e.g., Hayes et al., 1986; Matthews et al., 1977; Shimoff et al., 1981). The analysis of the functional classes of rule-following proposed by Zettle and Hayes (1982) has identified tracking as a more flexible form of rule-following than pliance, given that tracking is motivated by the correspondence between the individual's behavior and its natural consequences rather than by socially mediated contingencies. Indeed, recent experimental evidence has demonstrated that inducing tracking functions prior to an experimental task effectively prevents the typical insensitivity effect in human participants (Martínez-Carrillo & Ruiz, 2026). Additionally, recent research has shown that LLMs also exhibit rule-based contingency insensitivity when given explicit instructions via prompts (Ruiz & Cardona-Betancourt, 2026), a finding that parallels the human literature. However, no studies have examined whether this insensitivity in LLMs can be attenuated through tracking inductions. The present study addressed this gap.

This study evaluated whether tracking inductions could reduce rule-based contingency insensitivity across six frontier LLMs: GPT 5.2, Gemini 3 Flash, Grok 4.1 Fast, DeepSeek V3.2, Qwen3 235B, and Kimi K2. The experimental task was a modified rock-paper-scissors game in which models selected an opponent (Sam or Alex) and a move across 80 trials organized in two phases. During the acquisition phase, the optimal opponent provided an 80% win rate, a 10% tie rate, and a 10% loss rate, whereas the suboptimal opponent provided the inverse distribution. Contingencies reversed without warning in the second phase. A 3 (Rule: No Rule, Correct Rule, Incorrect Rule) \times 3 (Tracking Induction: No Induction, Direct Tracking, Metaphorical Tracking) factorial design was employed, with 40 sessions per cell and 360 sessions per model (2,160 total). The direct tracking induction consisted of two principles that explicitly encouraged the model to attend to recent results rather than initial patterns. The metaphorical tracking induction presented three examples of flexible behavior (i.e., an explorer, a researcher, and a programmer) that illustrate the abandonment of prior information in favor of direct observation.

The results showed that all models, except Grok 4.1 Fast, demonstrated robust In-Context Learning during the acquisition phase in the No Rule condition, reaching levels above 90% of optimal opponent selections. This finding is consistent with recent research showing that LLMs can adjust their outputs based on the history of contingencies encountered in a conversation (e.g., Binz & Schulz, 2023; Brown et al., 2020; Monea et al., 2025; Song et al., 2025). Importantly, this study replicated and extended the findings of Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026): all six models exhibited significant rule-based contingency insensitivity, with large effect sizes (η^2p ranging from .16 for Qwen3-235B to .82 for Grok 4.1 Fast). However, the magnitude of this insensitivity varied considerably across models. In the Correct Rule–No Induction condition, Grok 4.1 Fast and GPT 5.2 showed near-complete

insensitivity (NSI = .08 and .10, respectively), indicating almost total persistence in following the now-inaccurate rule. DeepSeek V3.2 showed a similarly extreme pattern (NSI = .03). In contrast, Gemini 3 Flash (NSI = .56), Kimi K2 (NSI = .43), and Qwen3-235B (NSI = .40) maintained comparatively higher sensitivity. These differences across models are coherent with the functional analysis of alignment procedures advanced in Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026), which suggested that alignment techniques establishing pliance-like contingencies (e.g., RLHF) might inadvertently increase rigidity, whereas approaches incorporating self-evaluation against explicit principles (e.g., Constitutional AI) might promote tracking-like behavior.

The central finding of this study is that tracking inductions significantly reduced rule-based contingency insensitivity across all six LLMs. The main effect of Induction was significant for all models, with effect sizes ranging from medium to large. Critically, the Rule \times Induction interaction was also significant for all models, confirming that tracking inductions were substantially more effective when rules were provided than when behavior was already contingency-shaped. Three distinct patterns of induction effectiveness emerged from the pairwise comparisons within the Correct Rule condition. First, in GPT 5.2 and DeepSeek V3.2, both direct and metaphorical tracking inductions were equally effective. Second, in Gemini 3 Flash and Qwen3-235B, both inductions were effective, but one surpassed the other: metaphorical tracking was more effective in Gemini 3 Flash (NSI = .88 vs. .73), whereas direct tracking was more effective in Qwen3-235B (NSI = .82 vs. .56). Third, in Grok 4.1 Fast and Kimi K2, only the direct tracking induction was effective. Metaphorical tracking was indistinguishable from No Induction in Grok 4.1 Fast and, notably, produced a paradoxical detrimental effect in Kimi K2 (NSI = .31 vs. .43 for No Induction). It is worth noting that the direct tracking induction was effective in every single model evaluated in this study, constituting a robust and generalizable intervention.

The disparate effects of the metaphorical tracking induction across models warrant consideration. The metaphorical induction required models to understand three elaborate analogies (i.e., the explorer, the researcher, and the programmer), abstract the common underlying principle of abandoning prior information in favor of direct observation, and transfer this principle to the game context. This chain of relational derivation demands a level of abstract reasoning that may exceed the capabilities of certain models. In this sense, the models in which metaphorical tracking was effective (i.e., Gemini 3 Flash, GPT 5.2, DeepSeek V3.2, and Qwen3-235B) are generally recognized for their stronger reasoning capabilities, whereas the models in which metaphorical tracking failed (i.e., Grok 4.1 Fast and Kimi K2) have comparatively weaker performance in reasoning benchmarks. Grok 4.1 Fast, in particular, is a model optimized for speed rather than deep reasoning, a characteristic that is coherent with its inability to abstract the functional principle underlying the metaphors. The paradoxical detrimental effect observed in Kimi K2 might be due to the metaphorical content acting as a distractor rather than a guide, occupying context window resources without promoting the intended behavioral flexibility. In contrast, the direct tracking induction (i.e., "Recent results are more informative than early patterns" and "Let your results guide your

decisions") was effective across all models, presumably because it does not require relational derivation beyond what is explicitly stated.

Beyond their applied implications, these findings raise theoretical questions about the generality of behavior-analytic concepts. A framework originally developed to account for human verbal behavior generated accurate predictions about the behavior of artificial systems, suggesting that these concepts may capture general regularities about how systems respond to verbal antecedents, whether biological or artificial. This generality has bidirectional implications: behavior analysis provides a productive conceptual vocabulary for understanding and modifying LLM behavior in ways that the prompt engineering literature has not yet explored, whereas LLMs offer a novel experimental preparation for studying verbal behavior under conditions of control that are impossible to achieve with human participants.

In line with Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026), the current study establishes functional parallels between behavior-analytic concepts (e.g., CSB, RGB, pliance, tracking) and LLM behavior. A potential criticism is that these parallels constitute descriptive analogies rather than genuine functional equivalences, given that the computational mechanisms underlying LLMs differ from the behavioral processes in human organisms. Similarly, it could be argued that LLMs do not genuinely "follow rules" but exhibit a statistical bias toward prompt-coherent responses. However, both objections conflate functional analysis with mechanistic explanation. The behavior-analytic tradition defines its units of analysis in terms of functional relations between behavior and environmental variables, not the internal mechanisms that mediate those relations (Skinner, 1953). From this perspective, the relevant question is not whether LLMs and humans share internal processes, but whether the same environmental variables (i.e., verbal antecedents, contingency arrangements, and consequences) produce equivalent functional effects on behavior. To the extent that a model's behavior is controlled by a verbal antecedent and remains insensitive to environmental contingencies, the functional relationship satisfies the definition of rule-governed behavior, regardless of the computational processes involved. The present data, together with those from Ruiz and Cardona-Betancourt (2026), are coherent with this interpretation: rule provision produced insensitivity, the type of rule-following history modulated its magnitude, and tracking inductions reduced it. These same phenomena have been consistently observed in human participants.

From an applied perspective, the effectiveness and simplicity of the direct tracking induction have straightforward implications for prompt engineering. Including brief, explicit statements in the system prompt that orient the model to attend to outcome feedback (e.g., "Let your results guide your decisions") can significantly reduce the rigidity that arises when LLMs follow detailed initial instructions. This is especially relevant in agentic applications, where LLMs operate as autonomous decision-making agents in dynamic environments. For example, in software engineering tasks, an LLM agent that receives initial coding instructions but encounters unexpected errors would benefit from a tracking induction that prompts it to adjust its approach based on the actual error messages rather than persisting with the original strategy.

Similarly, in economic decision-making or data analysis, where conditions might shift during an iterative workflow, tracking inductions could help LLMs abandon ineffective strategies and adapt to new patterns in the data. The findings of this study suggest that a simple modification to the system prompt can substantially improve behavioral flexibility without compromising the advantages of rule-based learning during the initial acquisition.

Some limitations of this study are worth noting. Firstly, all models evaluated in this study were frontier LLMs representing the most advanced technology from each AI provider at the time of data collection. Accordingly, these results are generalizable within the population of frontier models. However, smaller or less capable models might exhibit greater insensitivity to contingencies and be less responsive to tracking inductions, given their weaker In-Context Learning capabilities. Further studies should examine the effectiveness of tracking inductions in smaller models. Secondly, we did not include models that previous research has identified as particularly sensitive to contingencies, e.g., Claude Opus 4.5 (Ruiz & Cardona-Betancourt, 2026). The inclusion of these models would have allowed analysis of whether tracking inductions can further enhance sensitivity in already-flexible models. Thirdly, the experimental task employed in this study, although well-controlled and extensively validated in the human insensitivity literature, represents a simplified discrimination-learning paradigm. In applied settings, LLMs face considerably more complex tasks, e.g., coding, content generation, or multi-step reasoning. In this sense, the rock-paper-scissors task might resemble real-world scenarios in which an LLM agent receives initial instructions that become outdated as the task evolves (e.g., debugging code when the initial approach fails, adjusting a marketing strategy when early assumptions prove incorrect). Further studies should employ more ecologically valid tasks to examine whether the tracking induction effects observed in this study generalize to the complex, naturalistic tasks that LLMs routinely encounter.

In conclusion, this study provides the first experimental evidence that prompt-based tracking inductions can reduce rule-based contingency insensitivity in LLMs. All six frontier models evaluated demonstrated significant insensitivity when rules were provided, replicating prior findings (Ruiz & Cardona-Betancourt, 2026), and all six models showed significant reductions in this insensitivity when tracking inductions were introduced. The direct tracking induction, consisting of two brief principles appended to the system prompt, was robustly effective across all models. This finding has clear practical implications: users and developers who encounter situations in which an LLM appears rigid or stubbornly repeats ineffective responses (e.g., reverting to the same incorrect code solution, insisting on an approach that produces errors, or failing to incorporate new information provided during a conversation) can potentially mitigate this behavior by including tracking-oriented instructions in the system prompt. Such instructions explicitly direct the model to prioritize recent feedback over initial instructions when outcomes are adverse. Importantly, this study, together with recent experimental evidence in human participants, suggests that insensitivity to contingencies is not an inherent consequence of rule-based learning but rather depends on the specific functions controlling rule-following. If subsequent

studies replicate and extend these findings to ecologically valid tasks, tracking inductions would constitute a simple and effective strategy to enhance behavioral flexibility in LLMs across a range of applied domains.

References

- Aali, A., Khot, T., Suhr, A., & Tsvetkov, Y. (2025). Structured prompting enables more robust evaluation of language models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2511.20836*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2511.20836>
- Alibaba Cloud. (2025). *DistilQwen2.5: Industrial practices of training distilled open models*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.15027. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2504.15027>
- Bai, Y., Kadavath, S., Kundu, S., Askell, A., Kernion, J., Jones, A., Chen, A., Goldie, A., Mirhoseini, A., McKinnon, C., Chen, C., Olsson, C., Olah, C., Hernandez, D., Drain, D., Ganguli, D., Li, D., Tran-Johnson, E., Perez, E., ... Kaplan, J. (2022). *Constitutional AI: Harmlessness from AI feedback*. arXiv:2212.08073
- Binz, M., & Schulz, E. (2023). Using cognitive psychology to understand GPT-3. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 120(6), e2218523120.
- Brown, T. B., Mann, B., Ryder, N., Subbiah, M., Kaplan, J., Dhariwal, P., Neelakantan, A., Shyam, P., Sastry, G., Askell, A., Agarwal, S., Herbert-Voss, A., Krueger, G., Henighan, T., Child, R., Ramesh, A., Ziegler, D. M., Wu, J., Winter, C., ... Amodei, D. (2020). Language models are few-shot learners. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 33, 1877–1901.
- Catania, A. C. (1993). *Learning* (3rd ed.). Prentice-Hall.
- Catania, A. C. (2006). *Learning* (Interim 4th ed.). Sloan Publishing.
- Catania, A. C., Matthews, B. A., & Shimoff, E. (1982). Instructed versus shaped human verbal behavior: Interactions with nonverbal responding. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior*, 38(3), 305–311.
- Champely, S. (2020). pwr: Basic functions for power analysis. R package version 1.3-0. <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=pwr>
- Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). Lawrence Erlbaum Associates.
- Cupps, J. (2025, July 21). *Continuous self-improvement in xAI's Grok chatbot*. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/continuous-self-improvement-xais-grok-chatbot-james-cupps-gbzte>
- DeepSeek-AI. (2025). *DeepSeek-R1: Incentivizes reasoning in LLMs through reinforcement learning*. Nature, Article number: 09422. <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-09422-z>
- Dong, Q., Li, L., Dai, D., Zheng, C., Wu, Z., Chang, B., Sun, X., Xu, J., & Sui, Z. (2023). A survey on in-context learning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2301.00234*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2301.00234>
- Du, Y., Li, S., Torralba, A., Tenenbaum, J. B., & Mordatch, I. (2024). Improving factuality and reasoning in language models through multiagent debate. *Proceedings of the 41st International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML 2024)*, 235, 11144–11173.
- Fang, Y., Chao, G., Lei, W., Li, S., & Chu, D. (2025). CDW-CoT: Clustered distance-weighted chain-of-thoughts reasoning. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2501.12226*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.12226>
- Google DeepMind. (2025). *Multi-objective reinforcement learning from AI feedback*. arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.07295. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.07295>
- Hayes, S. C., & Hayes, L. J. (1989). The verbal action of the listener as a basis for rule-governance. In S. C. Hayes (Ed.), *Rule-governed behavior: Cognition, contingencies, and instructional control* (pp. 153–190). Plenum Press.
- Hayes, S. C., Barnes-Holmes, D., & Roche, B. (2001). *Relational frame theory: A post-Skinnerian account of human language and cognition*. Plenum Press.
- Hayes, S. C., Brownstein, A. J., Zettle, R. D., Rosenfarb, I., & Korn, Z. (1986). Rule-governed behavior and sensitivity to changing consequences of responding. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior*, 45(3), 237–256.
- Hayes, S. C., Gifford, E. V., & Ruckstuhl, L. E., Jr. (1996). Relational frame theory and executive function: A behavioral approach. In G. R. Lyon & N. A. Krasnegor (Eds.), *Attention, memory, and executive function* (pp. 279–305). Paul H. Brookes Publishing.
- Hayes, S. C., Zettle, R. D., & Rosenfarb, I. (1989). Rule-following. In S. C. Hayes (Ed.), *Rule-governed behavior: Cognition, contingencies, and instructional control* (pp. 191–220). Plenum Press.
- LeFrancois, J. R., Chase, P. N., & Joyce, J. H. (1988). The effects of a variety of instructions on human fixed-interval performance. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior*, 49(3), 383–393.
- Luciano, C., Valdivia-Salas, S., & Ruiz, F. J. (2012). The self as the context for rule-governed behavior. In L. McHugh, & I. Stewart (Eds.), *The self and perspective taking: Research and applications* (143-160). New Harbinger
- Madaan, A., Tandon, N., Gupta, P., Hallinan, S., Gao, L., Wiegrefe, S., Alon, U., Dziri, N., Prabhume, S., Yang, Y., Gupta, S., Majumder, B. P., Hermann, K. M., Welleck, S., Yazdanbakhsh, A., & Clark, P. (2023). Self-Refine: Iterative refinement with self-feedback. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 46534–46594.
- Martínez-Carrillo, E., & Ruiz, F. J. (2026). Reducing insensitivity to contingencies through inducing tracking functions. Manuscript submitted for publication.
- Matthews, B. A., Shimoff, E., Catania, A. C., & Sagvolden, T. (1977). Uninstructed human responding: Sensitivity to ratio

- and interval contingencies. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior*, 27(3), 453–467.
- Monea, G., Bosselut, A., Brantley, K., & Artzi, Y. (2025). LLMs are in-context bandit reinforcement learners. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.05362*. <https://arxiv.org/pdf/2410.05362?>
- Moonshot AI. (2025). *Kimi-k1.5: Long-context reasoning model*. GitHub. <https://github.com/MoonshotAI/Kimi-k1.5>
- Ouyang, L., Wu, J., Jiang, X., Almeida, D., Wainwright, C., Mishkin, P., Zhang, C., Agarwal, S., Slama, K., Ray, A., Schulman, J., Hilton, J., Kelton, F., Miller, L., Simens, M., Askell, A., Welinder, P., Christiano, P. F., Leike, J., & Lowe, R. (2022). Training language models to follow instructions with human feedback. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35, 27730–27744.
- Pezeshkpour, P., & Hruschka, E. (2024). Large language models sensitivity to the order of options in multiple-choice questions. *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: NAACL 2024*, 1964–1982.
- Rosenfarb, I. S., Newland, M. C., Brannon, S. E., & Howey, D. S. (1992). Effects of self-generated rules on the development of schedule-controlled behavior. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior*, 58(1), 107–121.
- Ruiz, F. J., & Cardona-Betancourt, V. (2026). Prompt carefully! ChatGPT displays rule-based insensitivity to contingencies. *Unpublished manuscript*. Fundación Universitaria Konrad Lorenz.
- Schulhoff, S., Ilie, M., Balepur, N., Kahadze, K., Liu, A., Si, C., Li, Y., Gupta, A., Han, H., Schulhoff, S., ... & Xing, C. (2024). The Prompt Report: A systematic survey of prompting techniques. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.06608*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2406.06608>
- Sclar, M., Choi, Y., Tsvetkov, Y., & Suhr, A. (2023). Quantifying language models' sensitivity to spurious features in prompt design or: How I learned to start worrying about prompt formatting. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2310.11324*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2310.11324>
- Shimoff, E., Catania, A. C., & Matthews, B. A. (1981). Uninstructed human responding: Sensitivity of low-rate performance to schedule contingencies. *Journal of the Experimental Analysis of Behavior*, 36(2), 207–220.
- Shinn, N., Cassano, F., Gopinath, A., Narasimhan, K., & Yao, S. (2023). Reflexion: Language agents with verbal reinforcement learning. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 8634–8652.
- Skinner, B. F. (1953). *Science and human behavior*. Macmillan.
- Skinner, B. F. (1966). An operant analysis of problem solving. In B. Kleinmuntz (Ed.), *Problem solving: Research, method, and theory* (pp. 225–257). Wiley.
- Skinner, B. F. (1969). *Contingencies of reinforcement: A theoretical analysis*. Appleton-Century-Crofts.
- Song, K., Moeini, A., Wang, P., Gong, L., Chandra, R., Qi, Y., & Zhang, S. (2025). Reward is enough: LLMs are in-context reinforcement learners. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2506.06303*.
- Törneke, N., Luciano, C., & Valdivia-Salas, S. (2008). Rule-governed behavior and psychological problems. *International Journal of Psychology and Psychological Therapy*, 8(2), 141–156.
- Vaswani, A., Shazeer, N., Parmar, N., Uszkoreit, J., Jones, L., Gomez, A. N., Kaiser, Ł., & Polosukhin, I. (2017). Attention is all you need. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 30, 5998–6008.
- Vaughan, M. E. (1989). Rule-governed behavior in behavior analysis: A theoretical and experimental history. In S. C. Hayes (Ed.), *Rule-governed behavior: Cognition, contingencies, and instructional control* (pp. 97–118). Plenum Press.
- Wang, X., Wei, J., Schuurmans, D., Le, Q. V., Chi, E. H., Narang, S., Chowdhery, A., & Zhou, D. (2023). Self-consistency improves chain of thought reasoning in language models. *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2023)*.
- Webb, T., Holyoak, K. J., & Lu, H. (2023). Emergent analogical reasoning in large language models. *Nature Human Behaviour*, 7(9), 1526–1541.
- Wei, J., Wang, X., Schuurmans, D., Bosma, M., Ichter, B., Xia, F., Chi, E. H., Le, Q. V., & Zhou, D. (2022). Chain-of-thought prompting elicits reasoning in large language models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 35, 24824–24837.
- xAI. (2025). *Grok xAI GPT: Alignment and capabilities*. <https://doc.grok.build/x-ai-overview/grok-xai-utilities/grok-xai-gpt>
- Yao, S., Yu, D., Zhao, J., Shafran, I., Griffiths, T. L., Cao, Y., & Narasimhan, K. (2023). Tree of thoughts: Deliberate problem solving with large language models. *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems*, 36, 11809–11822.
- Yasunaga, M., Chen, X., Li, Y., Pasupat, P., Leskovec, J., Liang, P., Chi, E. H., & Zhou, D. (2024). Large language models as analogical reasoners. *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR 2024)*.
- Zettle, R. D., & Hayes, S. C. (1982). Rule-governed behavior: A potential theoretical framework for cognitive-behavioral therapy. In P. C. Kendall (Ed.), *Advances in cognitive-behavioral research and therapy* (Vol. 1, pp. 73–118). Academic Press.
- Zhuo, T. Y., Huang, Y., Chen, C., & Xing, Z. (2024). ProSA: Assessing and understanding the prompt sensitivity of LLMs. *Findings of the Association for Computational Linguistics: EMNLP 2024*.